

**EXPLORATION OF THE PROCESSES OF NEW INDEPENDENT
RISE IN UZBEK JOURNALISM: PROBLEMS AND SKILLS ISSUES (
EXAMPLE OF THE ACTIVITY OF PRINTED PUBLICATIONS)**

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ANNOTATION

The article includes the problems of new development processes in Uzbek journalism, their coverage and analytical indicators. This teaching aims to explain and teach the new development processes of Uzbek journalism, starting from the beginning of the activity of Uzbek publications. The problems to be shown due to the coverage of the new development processes in journalism, their solutions and solutions, as well as the issues of skills that are acceptable, tangible and allow teachers and students to understand, are important for use.

KEY WORDS: Development, journalism, values, borders of our country, tolerance, principles, independence;

INTRODUCTION

During the next years of our independent development, under the leadership of the President of our republic, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Uzbekistan entered a new stage of development, a period of national growth. Thanks to the wide -scale reforms implemented in this regard, many changes are visible in the life of our people, people's outlook and thinking are growing. A number of new values and traditions are being formed for the further improvement of democratic reforms and the development of civil society. After our country gained independence, the main strategic goal was to build a legal democratic state based on a market economy and strengthen a free civil society. During the years of independence of our republic, many effective works were carried out. These include building a

state based on national statehood, strengthening its sovereignty, law and order, security, the inviolability of our country's borders, the rule of law, human rights and freedoms, creating an environment of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, peaceful living of our people, and implementation of the creative works of our citizens. These include things like doing.

The large-scale reforms carried out in our country during the years of independence are an important foundation for strengthening our national statehood and its sovereignty, ensuring security and law and order, the inviolability of our country's borders, the rule of law in society, human rights and freedoms, an environment of international harmony and religious tolerance. happened, created the necessary conditions and opportunities for our people to live a prosperous and happy life, to realize the creative potential of our citizens.

MAIN PART

The processes of the rise of new Uzbekistan are one of the important issues to be covered in journalism, and the problems and skill requirements that embody these processes require a lot of attention. On the example of the activity of printed publications, through articles and materials, the specific features of new growth processes, their development stages, organizational processes, systematically carried out reforms and indicated directions are observed.

The purpose of the teaching is to teach the new growth and development processes in Uzbek journalism, to understand the new Uzbek publications, students and experts and to teach them about these processes. Helping to put 'l. For the development of education, the task of cooperation with new directions of Uzbek journalism, educational centers and research institutes is of great importance.

The article on the topic "Illumination of the processes of the rise of the new Uzbekistan in Uzbek journalism: problems and skill issues (as an example of the activity of print publications)" is very important and it is very important to show

its problems, skill requirements, as well as the example of the activity of print publications. 'requires attention. The problems and skill issues related to the coverage of the processes of the rise of New Uzbekistan in journalism are one of the important topics in the field of Uzbek journalism related to the new advancements of Uzbek journalism and their importance.

The way of independent development of Uzbekistan can be divided into two periods, as was explained by our President when summarizing the results achieved during the years of independence in terms of the implementation of reforms to build a new society . That is, the initial stage, which includes the first reforms and changes related to the formation of the foundations of national statehood, the development model and development principles - 1991-2000, left a huge mark in our country and is literally of historical importance. is a transition period that has The second stage after 2001 - radical changes and great creative works that are being implemented in the construction of a democratic state and civil society, active changes, which have become extremely important in ensuring the consistent reform of all spheres of life. is a period. Historically, this period is short, the years of independence, based on the "Concept of Deepening Democratic Reforms and Civil Society Development in Our Country", as well as in the economic, political and spiritual spheres for our people for a period of time equal to the age of a teenager, are all-round development for our country and people. and no one today can deny that there was a period of ascension.

In the course of historical development, a number of types of press were established by private individuals, social groups (political currents, parties, trade unions, cultural-administrative organizations, etc.), joint-stock societies, government institutions and others and served their purposes. In the early days of the establishment of the press in Europe, the church widely used printed books and leaflets to promote religious ideology. Secular press was formed and began to

develop widely against the backdrop of increasingly limited influence of the church on the spiritual life of society. The service of the progressive press was great in the struggle for the establishment of an advanced social system and democratic procedures.

The press was formed in Uzbekistan in the second half of the 19th century. "Turkestanskiye vedomosti" and "Gazette of Turkestan Region" established in Tashkent in 1870 by the country's colonial rulers are the first examples of the press in Central Asia. In Turkestan, the first progressive national newspapers began to operate in 1905-07 ("Taraqqi", "Khurshid", "Shuhrat", etc.). Their path was continued by "Sadoi Turkistan", "Sadoi Fergana", "Najot" newspapers, and "Oyina" magazine published in the 2nd decade of the 20th century. National publications promoted the ideas of turning Turkestan into a literate, enlightened, developed, prosperous and independent country.

After 1917, as in all allied republics of the former USSR, a multi-branch system of party-Soviet press of a new political orientation was established in Uzbekistan. Contrary to general democratic rules, the process of formation and development of the press took place under conditions of one-party rule - the absolute monopoly of the Communist Party. The appearance and direction of newspapers, magazines, books were determined based on the instructions of the leadership of this ruling party.

Thanks to independence, a qualitatively new stage of democratic development has begun in the national development of Uzbekistan. Now, organizations, parties, associations, some communities, citizens also have the right to establish press publications. An opportunity was created to ensure freedom of the press in the country. Social-political fund for democratization and support of the mass media of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established in order

to create conditions for the normal functioning of mass media, solve financial and technical issues related to their publication and distribution, and provide practical support for active participation of creators in the democratic process. (August 30, 1996). This foundation is an independent, self-governing, non-governmental organization of media representatives.

of the Republic of Uzbekistan "[On [Publishing](#) Activities" (August 30, 1996), "On Mass Media" (December 26, 1997), "[On Protection of [Journalistic Activities](#)" (April 24, 1997), "[Information](#) "On guarantees and freedom of access" (April 24, 1997) played an important role in the development of Uzbekistan.

The State Press Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has been the general leader of the press work of the Republic of Uzbekistan, was reorganized as the Press and Information Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving management in the field of press and information" (July 3, 2002). Accordingly, the press and information agency of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional administrations of press and information were established in the presence of regional hokims. This reform was a major step forward in the direction of the democratization and liberalization of the country's social life, to more fully satisfy the information needs of the republic's population, to support the large-scale development of mass media, publishing and printing, and to form a modern market of information services.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion , it can be said that the problems and skill issues related to the coverage of the processes of the rise of the new Uzbekistan in journalism are one of the important topics in the field of Uzbek journalism regarding the new advancements of Uzbek journalism and their importance.

It is recommended to carry out activities and scientific research in order to allow for new developments in the field of Uzbek journalism and increase their understanding through the indicators and teachings covered in the article. The article, through the analysis of these important topics, shows what steps should be taken to prepare specialists and students for the developments in the new Uzbek journalism.

Uzbekistan aims to write an article on the problem of coverage of the new development processes in journalism. In this article, the specific features of Uzbekistan's new growth processes, their stages of development, organizational processes, problems on the subject of systematic reforms and indicated directions, and their presentation on the basis of the opposition, as well as experiences on the subject of skill requirements and theoretical skills are introduced.

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